

SURVEY ASSESSMENT CHECKLIST

We used the checklist of Molléri et al. [109] to assess our survey. Each of the checklist items has been rated as fully addressed (F), partially addressed (P), not addressed (N) or not applicable (NA). As suggested by Molléri et al. [109], we also provide our reasoning behind the scores. In total, 33 items were fully addressed. One item was partially addressed and the remaining four items were not applicable.

Resulting scores from our assessment using the checklist [109]

Item	Question	Score	Reasoning
1	Research objectives		
1A	Are the research objectives expressed in measurable terms?	F	Yes, the overall research goal and corresponding research questions are stated in Section 1. The survey questions are mapped to the research questions (Section 3.1.1).
1B	Is the research context defined? Does it consider a reasonable set of objectives?	F	Yes, the research context is defined in Section 1 and the case company is described in Section 2. The research questions are relevant and within the scope of our study.
1C	Is the need for survey research motivated?	F	Yes, we reviewed related work and identified a need for more detailed insights into the perceptions of software experts on factors affecting delays in agile projects.
2	Study plan		
2A	Is the survey process conducted based upon detailed procedures?	F	Yes, we followed the guidelines from Kitchenham and Pfleeger [70], and Kasunic [71], to design and execute our surveys.
2B	Is there a reflection on the need to update the research plan?	NA	
2C	Are the roles and responsibilities of researchers and other stakeholders defined?	F	Yes, the responsibilities of the authors in designing survey questions and manual coding are described in Sections 3.1.1, 3.1.4 and 7.
3	Identify population		
3A	Is the population or the survey's target audience characterized?	F	Yes, the target population was composed of all employees that are part of the development teams at ING TECH (Section 3.1.3).
3B	Is the size of the population stated? If it is not possible to gather this data, are statistic estimates of the population drawn?	F	Yes, 2850 employees in software engineering and project management (Section 3.1.3).
4	Sampling plan		
4A	Is the kind of sample (i.e., probabilistic, non-probabilistic) defined?	F	Yes, the probabilistic sample is described in Section 3.1.3.
4B	Is the sampling process described, and the resulting sample size presented?	F	Yes, the sampling process and the sample size (1400) is presented in Section 3.1.3.
4C	Are the sources of sampling defined?	F	Yes, the source (mailing list) is mentioned in Section 3.1.3.
4D	Are the strategies and criteria to select units (of observation, of analysis and search unit) stated?	F	Yes, the sampling frame is described in Section 3.1.3.
5	Instrument design		
5A	Is the type of instrument (i.e., self- or interview-administrated) defined?	F	Yes, we developed self-administrated online surveys (Section 3.1.1).
5B	Is the instrument design process (acquisition, development, prototyping, versioning, reuse) described in the project?	F	Yes, we developed the surveys and explained our design decisions in Section 3.1.1.
5C	Are the demographic questions formulated according to the audience?	F	Yes, the demographic questions were formulated to collect information on respondents' roles and experience (Section 3.1.1). These characteristics are important to assess in software engineering research [71].
5D	Has special care been taken to make the questions understandable by the respondents?	F	Yes, we have taken several measures to make the survey questions understandable by the respondents (Section 3.1.1).
5E	Has special care been taken to avoid intrusive and unethical questions?	F	Yes, we let participants know that the responses would be kept confidential and that they would only be evaluated in aggregated form (Section 7).
5F	Is the number and order of the questions taken into consideration? Is it possible to use different versions of the instrument in case of a potential bias about the order of the questions identified.	F	Yes, we kept the number of survey questions (5) to a minimum (Section 3.1.1). We phrased and ordered the questions in a sequential order of activities to avoid leading questions. The factors in the second survey were presented in random order to reduce ordering bias.
5G	Is there a reflection on the type of responses (i.e., open-ended, close-ended or a mix of both) required for the questions?	F	Yes, we provided an explanation and motivation for the type of questions used (mix of open-ended and close-ended) in Section 3.1.1.
5H	If employing close-ended questions, are the standardized response formats (i.e., nominal, ordinal, interval or ratio) stated? Appropriate scales should be attributed to the questions according to the mapped variables.	F	Yes, we used Likert scale questions from "no impact" to "large impact" to assess the perceived impact levels of factors.
5I	Is there a reflection on the adoption of additional sources for data collection? Such additional sources may provide means for characterizing strata of participants or for validating data through cross-verification and triangulation.	F	Yes, we had an overview of teams (team names) participants belonged to. This enabled us to determine members' participation and link survey responses to teams' repository data for triangulation.

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6	Instrument validation		
6A	Is the validation process of the survey instrument detailed?	F	Yes, we piloted both surveys with 25 randomly selected employees from ING TECH. We refined our survey questions based on the outcome of the pilot run (Section 3.1.2).
6B	Is the instrument measuring what is intended? Are the questionnaire items mapped to the research question(s)?	F	Yes, the survey questions are mapped to the research questions (Section 3.1.1). To evaluate whether the instrument measures what it is intended to, we sought support from the second (confirmatory) survey and performed data triangulation.
6C	In the case of an electronic or online questionnaire, is the usability evaluated?	P	This was partially addressed via the pilot study. Participants were asked to provide their feedback on the survey contents (open-ended question), which implicitly covered usability aspects.
6D	Are the results of the instrument validation discussed? After the main problems been identified, were the instruments updated/amended according to the validation results?	F	Yes, we updated the survey instruments based on the validation results (Section 3.1.2).
7	Participant recruitment		
7A	Are the strategies to select participants (stage 4. Sampling plan) implemented?	F	Yes, as per our sampling plan, the participants were invited using personal invitations (Section 3.1.3).
7B	Are the ancillary documents (e.g., invitation, cover and thank you letter) provided?	F	Yes, the participants were invited using a personal invitation mail featuring the purpose of the survey. A thank you message was presented upon completion of the survey.
7C	If rewards or incentives are provided to respondents, are the reasons and implications (e.g., ethical concerns, biases) discussed?	NA	
8	Response management		
8A	Are the responses monitored? E.g., response rate, non-responsiveness, and drop-out questions. In case of inadequate response rate, were the reasons for non-responses and drop-out items investigated?	F	Yes, the response rates for survey 1 (21%) and survey 2 (24%) are comparable to the response rates of other software engineering surveys (Section 3.1.3).
8B	Is there any action to be taken in case of non-responses (e.g., reminders)? If reminders are employed, is the process for selecting and inviting new participants described? Moreover, are the implications of reminders discussed?	F	Yes, we sent reminder emails to non-responders to increase the response rate and reduce the possibility of bias. We discussed the reminders in Section 3.1.3 and their implications in Section 7.
9	Data analysis		
9A	Is the data validated prior to analysis?	F	Yes, the “not applicable” responses were omitted from the analysis set (Section 3.1.4). During manual coding, incomplete responses to RQ1.3 were marked as having ‘no explicit relationship’.
9B	Is the method for data analysis specified? Are the steps of the analysis process described? Are they suitable for the response formats collected?	F	Yes, Section 3.1.4 covers these aspects. For the Likert scale questions (RQ1.2), we used descriptive statistics to order the factors by their perceived level of impact. For the open-ended questions, we performed manual coding.
9C	If statistical analysis is employed, is the hypothesis testing process documented and the standardized responses presented?	NA	
9D	If using qualitative synthesis (e.g., meta-ethnography, thematic or content analysis), is it clear how the categories/themes were derived?	F	Yes, Section 3.1.4 covers these aspects and includes coding samples.
9E	If a stratified sample is defined, are the data analysed according to demographics? Are there meaningful comparisons drawn from them?	NA	
10	Reporting		
10A	Are the instrument and ancillary documents accessible to readers? If not, are the reasons for that discussed and convincing? If data resulting from the survey were disclosed, were anonymity and confidentiality of data discussed?	F	The final survey instruments can be found in the supplemental material [72]. The implications of the non-anonymous settings of the surveys are discussed in Section 7.
10B	Has a discussion of both positive and negative findings been demonstrated? Is the discussion addressing the research question(s) or hypothesis? Does the discussion take into consideration the generalization of findings?	F	Yes, we discussed our main findings and answers to the research questions in Section 6. The generalizability of the findings are discussed in Section 7.
10C	Are the results of the assessment checklist reported? Are limitations of the study (e.g., threats to validity) discussed?	F	Yes, we refer to the scores from this assessment in Section 7. We also used the checklist to identify threats to validity, which are discussed in the same section.
10D	Are the conclusions justified by the results? Furthermore, are the implications and potential use of the results discussed?	F	Yes, our conclusions are based on our findings. The factors and types of relationships come from open-ended responses, and we rigorously assessed the expressed mechanisms through manual coding. We discussed the implications of our results for research and practice in Sections 5 and 6.